

THE MAIN REPRESENTATIVES OF THE UZBEK TRANSLATION
SCHOOL

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Annotation

This article is devoted to history of the development of the Uzbek translation school and their main representatives. The main period in and the reasons of the development of translation is clarified in this research. This article also gives information about the works of writers and transleologists on translations in Uzbekistan.

Key words: translation, interpretation, transleology, transleologists, source language, target language

Translators have always played a key role in society. Medieval translators for example had a major impact on scholarship, and contributed to the development of vernacular languages and national identities around these languages. Translators went on playing a key role in the advancement of society for centuries. Translation is a communication of meaning from source language into target language.

The translator's role as a bridge for "carrying across" values between cultures has been discussed since Terence, a Roman playwright who adapted Greek comedies into Roman in the 2nd century BCE. The debate relating to sense-for-sense translation vs. word-for-word translation also started around that time. The term "sense for sense" is said to be Jerome in his "Letter to Pammachius". While translating the Bible into Latin (later known as the "Vulgate"), Jerome stated that the translator needed to translate "not word for word but sense for sense" ("non verbum e verbo sed sensum de sensu").

Cicero, a prominent philosopher and writer also famously cautioned against translating “word for word”. Cicero was also a translator from Greek to Latin, and compared the translator’s work to that of an artist. Large-scale translation efforts were also undertaken by the Arabs after they conquered the Greek Empire, to offer Arabic versions of all major Greek philosophical and scientific works. The second half of the 20th century saw the birth of a new discipline called “**Translation Studies**” as well as the creation of new institutes specializing in teaching it. Under the leadership of G. Salomov, most of the scholars contributed to the development of translation in Uzbekistan. In particular, the curriculum of "Translation History", “Translation of proverbs and idioms” (1961), "Fundamentals of translation theory", published in 1973, became the main program of teaching translation theory in higher educational institutions of the republic. He is the author of the textbook "Introduction into Translation Theory". Professor Gaybulla Salomov states on the basis of the thesis that translation is a linguistic, literary-aesthetic phenomenon, vocabulary, and translator is a creator as well as scholars who have started to create theoretical researches about translation studies [1].

In this cultural-literary interchange and interpenetration, **the Russian** language played the role of a bridge connecting the Uzbek reader with world culture and literature. The Uzbek school of translation of the last century was actually based on translations from Russian in its basic composition and practice. Consequently, English-language literature was also translated by means of the Russian language [2]. Practically there was no school of translation directly from English. The above specifics of the Uzbek school of translation are based on the following factors: **First**, the Uzbek school of translation was formed in the middle Ages and was one of the possibilities for the wide development of Islamic religion and culture. Subsequently, many representatives of the School of Science and Literature made a great contribution to the formation and development of Islamic civilization in many sciences. The work of the great encyclopedists of the time is a

clear indication of this. One of the characteristics of that time was the availability of translators and bilingual, as well as explanatory dictionaries.

Secondly, the development process of the Uzbek translation school has always been associated with the growth of national self-awareness and the manifestation of the ideas of the revival of national greatness, with the growth of the educational movement. Uzbek **enlighteners** sought to acquaint the reader with the greatest and immortal works that are included in the golden fund of world literature. Therefore, it is during the period of enlightenment that the first attempts of translations from Russian and other languages, including from English, appear.

Thirdly, the most developed period of the Uzbek school of translations falls on the second half of the XX century. It was during this period that the main principles, methodology, main directions of the Uzbek translation school and Uzbek transleology were formed as a scientific discipline. A number of transleologists and translators entered the literary scene. Also, many poets and writers engaged in translation activities. During this period, research was carried out on the peculiarities of literary translation, such transleologists as G.Salamov [3], S.Mamadzhanov, G.Hodjaev, N.Vladimirova, K.Juraev, N.Kamilov, S.Meliev, S.Azimov, Sh.Atabaev, S.Achilov, B.Ermatov, H.Ismailov, M. Bakaeva, N.Atajanov, K.Musaev, A.Muminov and others.

Amanjon Muminov emphasized to develop consecutive translation in students of foreign language faculty. He was the author of the manual which is called “A guide to consecutive translation.” In this book one can get useful information about improving oral translation skills in students [4].

The works of English poets and their translations into Uzbek gave a rise the process of translation in our country. It was during this period that hundreds of translations of world literary works by dozens of translators, writers and poets, such as Usman Nasyr, Sanjar Syddyk, Jumaniyaz Sharipov, Ninel Vladimirova, Mirzakalon Ismaili (more than 200 works of classics of Russian and Western literature), Gulnara Gafurova, Askad Mukhtar, Gafur Ghulam (Shakespeare,

“Othello”), M. Sheikhzade (Shakespeare, “Hamlet”, “Romeo and Juliet”, “King Lear”), Uygun (Shakespeare, “Julius Caesar”), Komil Yashen (Shakespeare, “Anthony and Cleopatra ”), Jamal Kamal (Shakespeare, “King Richard III”), Kadir Mirmukhamedov (G. Bocaccio, “Decameron”), ErkinVakhidov (Goethe, “Faust”), Abdulla Aripov (Dante, “The Divine Comedy”), Sh.Shamuhamedov (Firdousi, “Shahname” and Classics Persian literature).

The Spanish novelist **Cervantes**, famously known all over Europe for his “**Don Quixote**” (1605-15), expressed his own opinion on the translation process by offering a rather despairing metaphor for the end result of translations. Don Quixote has been translated into many languages of the world, including Uzbek. The work was translated into Uzbek from Russian version by **Sotiboldi Yoldoshev**.

In Uzbekistan special attention is given to the issues related to translation, especially training the translators who translate scientific, literary and other literature from Uzbek into English and other foreign languages into high quality and skill [5].

The translation theory and practice is taught as an independent and compulsory discipline in Tashkent state pedagogical university, foreign languages faculty. The students of this faculty are doing researches by following above mentioned scholars’ ideas. Some of the talented students published several manuals translating Uzbek folklore into English under the leadership of professor M.H.Alimova. The dean of the faculty, associate professor A.M.Mamadaliyev is conducting seminar trainings on developing oral translation skills among students.

In conclusion one can say that translation plays important role in the development of society. It can help us to improve the relationship between different countries. Only through the help of translation people can get acquainted with different nation and their culture, one can develop horizon and enlarge view point about the world [6]. The process of translation is developing day by day according to the efforts of outstanding linguists. But sometimes we may observe

some drawbacks in this process. In Uzbekistan there are a lot of scholars who contributed to the development of translation theory and practice. Thanks to them nowadays young generation is doing researches on translation following the works of above mentioned scholars.

The list of used literature

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